

THE ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN TEACHING LANGUAGES.

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Abstract: This article deals with what is media, how we use media, moreover, positive and negative aspects of media environment in the educational process.

Keywords: media, television, radio, book, magazine, newspaper.

INTRODUCTION

Using different means of Mass Media in foreign language lessons can provide teachers and students with creative and practical ideas. Media gives an opportunity to teachers to meet various needs and interests of the students. They also provide students with a lot of language practices through activities using magazines, radio, TV, movies, books, newspapers, Internet and tasks develop reading, writing, speaking and listening skills. Media helps with several issues such as: motivation, editing, recycling, drafting, clarity, revising, mixed-ability classes, variety, updating information in the book, giving life and color to lesson procedures and methods, thus at the same time helping the students improve fluency and accuracy.

The importance of media. Media is essential to get updated about our large consumer-driven society in a modern way. Media constantly updates a person about every technical, political, educational, art, business, and every field of our

social life. Media is also essential to spread advertisements about a product or other public elements.

Television. This time, we are not talking about virtual language training or e-learning exercises. No, we are talking about an activity we all do every day: Watching TV, Netflixing, binge-watching your favourite series. And as of now, you have a valid excuse too. Research shows that learners are more motivated to learn a language by watching TV in a foreign language. You improve your listening skills and even your pronunciation and grammar, all thanks to watching TV.

Radio. Radio educational programmes can provide good speakers of English to students and give them a very clear and interesting explanation of grammatical concepts. Interactive radio can help to improve speaking skill. Also, material can be recorded from it, preserved and played later to learners.

Book. Reading can give you a huge exposure to chunks of correct language which can both prepare the ground for, and reinforce, your speaking practice. Don't go to scientific literature or poetry for this, of course. Go for realistic dialogues in plays or dialogue-heavy novels. We know that reading to children has many benefits, and that books can be used to promote children's language. This is even more important for children who struggle with language and who need even more exposure to language. Your local library is a good place to access children's books. Librarians are a great source of information about books that might spark your child's interest and suit his or her developmental level. But your child is the best person to guide your book selection – your child will be most motivated by a book he has chosen himself.

Magazine. With colorful artwork and photos, magazines bring an array of content to life for young readers. Magazine pieces offer short text and can be used for instruction in many literacy skill areas. Students are exposed to a variety of texts that encourage them to read, listen, learn and interact with engaging content.

Newspaper. Similarly, print news tends to be well-written, with appropriate and correct use of grammar. The news enriches your mind culturally. As you learn the language, you're also learning important details about the countries in which the language is spoken.

CONCLUSION

Once again, it is worth saying that media plays a very important role in learning any foreign language. In particular, I think that teachers should also use media to make students interested in language. Because in today's age of modern technology, it is becoming more and more difficult to get children interested in reading. The only way to get their attention is to educate them on the techniques and social media they are interested in.

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